

FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION SYSTEM OF GROWING SOY VARIETIES IN AGRICULTURE

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Annotation. In the article, factors for its implementation and development of soy variety breeding system in agriculture are presented.

Key words. Soybeans, cultivation of soybean varieties, innovations, innovative technologies, seeds, next generation soybeans. Chorian countries.

The economic reforms implemented in the agriculture of our country are gradually solving the problems accumulated in the sector. Each stage of the reform has its own directions, and these directions are distinguished by the solution of existing problems. As the reform process deepens and the scale of the economy becomes more liberal, the main attention in the field is aimed at growing soybeans and increasing the amount of production, as well as selling it, increasing their competitiveness. It is possible to increase the competitiveness of soybean cultivation based on the results of research, by using modern techniques and technologies, organizing labor and production, increasing the efficiency of resources and maintaining ecological balance, or in general, the sustainable growth of the agricultural sector can be achieved through its scientific development.

Respulika is the main support for increasing the efficiency of soybean cultivation in agriculture and sustainable development of the country's agrarian economy. Recently, the problem of achieving and maintaining economic efficiency in agriculture is often related to reducing costs or rationalizing resource consumption in the soybean cultivation process. True, this problem, on the one hand, it would be wrong to deny that, first of all, the cost per unit in the process of soybean cultivation is related to the consumption of material and technical resources and its reduction. Nevertheless, to achieve the economic efficiency of soybean cultivation, choosing the direction related to the reduction of resource consumption and thus striving to achieve the goal will not be the only correct way.

An integrated approach to the problem of achieving the economic efficiency of soybean cultivation in agriculture, including the introduction of modern advanced technologies and innovations, is one of several directions related to finding a solution to the problem. A new idea or a new product is significant because it is created in a certain limited environment. This created product is also required to serve the interests of a certain group of people. Therefore, a high-level organization of the process of forming continuous mutually beneficial organizational-economic relations from the production of the created product to its delivery to the consumer can fully serve the interests of the parties.

With the help of this, in the development of scientific research, it will be appropriate to carry out research related to the issue of putting scientific developments into practice and their rational use. And the human factor plays a key role in managing this situation. Because the

basic law of economics is related to the extent to which the role of scientific potential is in the issue of providing unlimited needs of the population from limited resources in a given society. Conducting scientific research in agriculture and developing strategic directions for the development of the market of scientific products on this basis accelerates the introduction of the results of scientific and technical development activities into agricultural production, creates conditions for the formation of expanded reproduction on a scientific and technical basis, and conducts the policy of developing the agrarian economy in the country allows.

At a time when the population is growing in the country, there are urgent and responsible tasks, such as selecting varieties with high yield and strength from soybean varieties created by breeders in order to select varieties that are adapted to each climatic conditions and have a high potential yield, and apply them to production. Our country has its own soil and climate conditions according to its geographical location and regions. Therefore, new, promising local and foreign soybean varieties should be tested in field scientific-practical experiments. In addition, a new set of agrotechnological measures applied to local new soybean varieties should be developed based on the natural conditions of this place, recommended for the production process.

Among the field crops, soybean seeds are distinguished as a plant rich in vegetable oil, medicinal properties, vitamins, and most importantly, it has the property of increasing soil fertility, as well as high economic efficiency.

Therefore, it is one of the urgent issues to determine the optimal planting rate of soybean local varieties, to introduce improved technologies of cultivation in the fields of farms, which are of great importance in maintaining and increasing food, fodder and soil fertility.

It is known that reducing production costs per product unit is the main condition for agricultural profitability. This goal can be achieved by increasing the productivity of agricultural crops. In the cultivation of field crops for grain and seed, the irrigation method, effective use of fertilizers, weed control and a number of other factors are considered to be the most important factors in increasing productivity.

Before planting soybeans, as a rule, it is enough to carry out one cultivation immediately before planting the seeds at the planting depth. This cultivation should be combined with the application of soil herbicides for planting in the soil. Mineral fertilizers for soybeans, due to their high cost, should be applied taking into account the level of yield potential, rainfall and irrigation possibilities. It is necessary to take into account the level of natural soil fertility, the specific characteristics of various agricultural technologies, and a number of other factors.

All agrotechnical factors used in the cultivation of this soybean crop were taken into account to determine the economic efficiency of the cultivation of oilseed crops, including: pre-planting and planting costs, irrigation, fertilization, disease and pest control in relation to the sowing dates of the soybean varieties studied in this research work. fighting, as well as the costs of harvesting and transporting to grain enterprises are taken into account.

According to the results of the research, it should be noted that soybean cultivation is an economically effective crop, and also plays an important role in improving the financial and economic activity of farms. On the other hand, soybean cultivation on the scale of our republic has the potential to increase the amount of products obtained by directly improving its seed production system, fully complying with the rules of agrotechnical processing, increasing the yield by using the advanced achievements of science and technology, as well as increasing the economic potential of our country.

The organization and development of scientific-research works in the agricultural sector is related to the expansion of scientific-research and experimental design works and the implementation of its results.

It is related to strengthening the scientific potential of agriculture for soybean cultivation, increasing the level of providing agriculture with qualified personnel, introducing economic methods of the management mechanism, improving the organizational and economic mechanism of soybean cultivation.

The effectiveness of the implementation of the achievements of soybean cultivation is determined by a number of factors for the development and implementation of the system of cultivation of soybean varieties in agriculture. These factors include:

- implementation of scientific and technical innovations of soybean cultivation in agriculture, determined by best practices in the field of agriculture;
- is related to the production of scientific and technical innovations based on local conditions and based on innovative solutions;
- organizational-technological processes are interrelated through scientific development. As a result, it improves with the development of science and adaptation of scientific solutions to local conditions.

Soybean cultivation is an important part of agricultural production in the republic. The growing interest in soybean cultivation is related to the economic importance of agriculture, because soybean is a source of high-quality plant protein that is close to animal proteins. Processing products obtained from it, on the one hand, form the basis of a high-protein feed base for livestock, on the other hand, it is an indispensable raw material for various industries.

It is related to natural climatic conditions that are very favorable for the cultivation of soy and the presence of scientific institutions that conduct research on its processing products.

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